

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN SOCIETY AND THEIR SOCIAL ACTIVISM

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Annotation: the article describes the role of women in society, their activities in various spheres of society. The content of reforms aimed at supporting women is covered.

Keywords: social activity, unique patterns, entrepreneurship, reforms.

After independence, Uzbekistan began to focus on women from the first years. Increasing the role of women in society, the importance of an active woman and her exemplary behavior in society has become an urgent topic. Women and their role in the life of society have always been important criteria. The development of any state and society occurs on the basis of a number of factors. In these processes, the issue of women, their participation in socio-political relations, the fact that their rights and freedoms are practically ensured – is considered an important index of the development of states and democracy. Already, the woman and her place in the life of society have always been important criteria. Today, women fully demonstrate their intellectual and physical abilities in the socio-political, economic and spiritual spheres, contributing to the elevation of society's spirituality.

Due to the reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan, several works are being carried out to increase the role and status of women in society. The first president's statement, "increasing the role and status of our mothers, sisters, women and daughters in society, easing their work and lifestyle, should remain one of the main and priority tasks of our state, society"¹ his statement is proving itself.

Nowadays, many reforms are being carried out in the life of our society. All this is to glorify our women. Our society pays special attention to women. In particular, the head of state Sh.M. Mirziyoyev We can know from the following words of - speaking about the female breed, dear and moderate to all of us, first of all, we bow and bow before the mother's urine, which gave birth to us, gave us white milk and brought us up. The most worthy of the word Holy on Earth is the mother, first of all. Our people constantly glorify and ardently live mother urine. This is also evidenced by the fact that magnificent statues were erected in honor of mothers in our country"².

Tomaris, Zebiniso, Nodirabegim, Barchinoy, Bibikhonim, unique figures of Uzbek women, have become symbols of the Uzbek people with their ibo-imagination, intelligence, elegance.

Today's young women, who follow the above personalities, are currently engaged in an exemplary leader, teacher, educator, doctor and other professions. By focusing on women, it is

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti I.A.Karimovning "O'zbekiston Respublikasi davlat va jamiyat qurilishida xotin-qizlarning rolini oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" 1995-yil 2-martda qabul qilgan Farmoni.

² O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida (O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari to'plami-T.:2017.

also possible to solve the issues of raising society, raising a multifaceted and perfect generation.

In order to enrich the spiritual world of women, to spend their free time meaningfully, ghazalkhani nights, meeting of readers, etc. are held. At the meetings, the works of great ancestors such as Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Nasr Farabi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Imam al-Bukhari are widely discussed and conclusions are drawn. The processes of formation of spirituality in our country like this are expanding.

Women are engaged in the task of educating and educating mature and healthy generations in the field of Education. They are:

- integrity of the spiritual and economic system in education;
- love for the motherland, instilling the idea of Milli istiqlol, raising young people;
- formation of the spiritual consciousness of citizens;
- preserving and leaving the national and traditional traditions of the Uzbek people to the future generation;

they carry out cooperation with foreign specialists in the field of Education. Ensuring the active participation of women in socio-cultural life is carried out on a wide range of fronts. During the years of independence, the participation of women in socio-cultural processes in our Republic increased significantly. Such indicators are clearly visible in various fields of Science, Education, Culture.

Uzbekistan women's general level of knowledge is at a high level. In the total number of specialists with higher and secondary special education, women's swings exceed 50 percent.³ Therefore, given the growing technical improvement of production and the emergence of new industries in the conditions of market reforms and the growing need for qualified personnel, it is required to improve their re-education as a means of women's adaptation in the labor market. The implementation of the National Training Program for personnel for 1997-2005 made this widely possible.

As we said above, various reforms are being implemented to increase the activity of women in society. Women are trying themselves on different fronts. An example of this is the field of entrepreneurship.

Increasing the economic activity of women in a market economy requires the state and society to take special measures, develop long-term plans, programs. It is necessary to remember that in conditions of market relations based on competition, conflict of interest, not all women have the opportunity to fully demonstrate their abilities and potential. Sharp competition, complicated by the variety of properties, "who owns" does not allow everyone to realize their inner creative forces. In this place, it will be necessary to support enterprising women, help them in the development of their "work". Only a woman who owns private property is active in economic relations.

Private property forms positive social qualities in a person. To be economical, not to waste, to work with initiative, to end vices such as loyalty and laziness, to reward people according to their business acumen, to appreciate time is among such qualities. In the field of entrepreneurship, women both acquire the above qualities and benefit society. When it comes

³ Ubaydullayeva.R.A. Mustaqil O'zbekiston: ayol, oila va jamiyat. - T.: Fan, 2006.

to corruption in education, a thousand unfortunately continue to increase as much as it is fought against it.⁴

It should be noted again that in recent years, the work of ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of women, strengthening their role in society, implementing complex measures aimed at supporting the institution of the family has reached a new level of quality. Uzbekistan has joined all major international documents that protect women from any discrimination and abuse. Examples include the Geneva Convention on the protection of Motherhood, The New York conventions on the political rights of women, and the New York conventions on the elimination of all forms of discrimination in women's Rights, International documents such as the Declaration "on the Prevention of trafficking, especially the trade of women and children, which complements the United Nations Convention on Transnational Organized Crime, and Attention to women can also be seen through reforms and works aimed at ensuring the full extent of their rights and freedoms. These reforms are a sign of the incompetence of women's role in society.

⁴ Talantbek Madumarov, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Raximjon Ogli (2023). FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM). Educational sacrifices, 02-05 (1), 194-197.

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